

1 **Wetting and spreading behavior of liquid Si-Ti eutectic alloy in contact with**
2 **glassy carbon and SiC at T = 1450°C**

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21 **Abstract**

22 The contact heating sessile drop and capillary purification methods were applied for a fundamental
23 study concerning the wettability and reactivity of liquid Si-16.2at%Ti (eutectic composition) in
24 contact with Glassy Carbon and SiC at T = 1450°C under an Ar atmosphere. Different spreading
25 stages with different slopes, depending on the starting conditions of the materials used, were
26 observed. On the contrary, the final contact angle value seemed not affected and the equilibrium
27 contact values of $\theta \approx 44^\circ \pm 2$ and $\theta \approx 42^\circ \pm 2$ were displayed on Glassy Carbon and SiC,
28 respectively.

29 The solidified Si-Ti eutectics/GC and Si-Ti eutectics/SiC samples were examined both at the top of
30 the drop and at the cross-section by SEM/EDS. The presence of a SiC layer as unique reaction
31 product at the Si-Ti eutectics/GC interface, confirmed that wettability is mainly driven reactivity.
32 Contrarily, as non-reactive system, at the Si-Ti eutectics/SiC interface a weak dissolution of SiC
33 substrate was detected.

34 **1. Introduction**

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1 Nowadays, lightweight composites as structural materials emerge as promising candidates for
2 construction and assembling of lighter-weight transportation systems such as air and space crafts,
3 satellites, drones, high-speed trains, etc [1]. For such kind of advanced applications, a high
4 corrosion resistance and a set of excellent thermo-mechanical properties are the key requirements in
5 properly designing composites materials.

6 Currently, remarkable efforts are focused on the development of highly performant CMC or MMC-
7 type composites where the metal phase is an Al, Si, Mg or Ti-based alloy [1, 2] and SiC is the
8 refractory matrix or reinforcement.

9 A combination of SiC with metal phases compensates the poor workability and the brittleness of
10 ceramics. In parallel, the presence of SiC incorporated into a metal matrix (as particulates or fibers)
11 significantly increases the overall thermo-mechanical response [3, 4].

12 In the MMCs approach, high volume percentages of reinforcing agents are incorporated into various
13 intermetallic matrices to carry a major portion of the load. In addition, the presence of
14 reinforcements facilitate either crack deflection or increasing the fracture toughness of the
15 composites. MMC can be designed to have superior properties such as enhanced high-temperature
16 performance, outstanding thermo-mechanical response, increased wear resistance than those of
17 unreinforced metal matrix phase.

18 Both the constituent phases (metal matrix and SiC) are preliminarily considered on the basis of their
19 chemical stability, thermo-physical and thermo-mechanical properties.

20 On the other hand, the control of interfacial phenomena occurring between reinforcements and
21 metal matrix during the fabrication process, high temperature consolidation or even in service, is a
22 key issue and should be considered in a successful design of the composite. Indeed, some
23 interactions may cause interfacial instability degradation of the reinforcement properties and
24 formation of brittle interfacial reaction compounds, resulting in detrimental thermo-mechanical
25 properties.

26 There are a number of roadblocks that could potentially derail these efforts and keep composites
27 limited to aerospace or luxury vehicles. One roadblock that has always been discussed is the higher
28 cost of composites versus metals.

29 To produce such composites with desirable properties, the reactive infiltration process, belonging to
30 spontaneous/pressure-less infiltration mechanisms, possesses well known advantages over other
31 conventional and costly sintering and hot-pressing techniques i.e. lower processing temperatures,
32 shorter times and nearly-net shape fabrication capabilities [5-8]. In spontaneous infiltration, the
33 molten metal phase invades into the voids of the porous refractory material. A “compact”

1 microstructure can be easily obtained by controlling the process parameters (temperature, total
2 pressure, porosity etc.) and promoting good wetting characteristics crucial for self-permeation.
3 Many examples of composites obtained by infiltrating liquid Si and Si-based alloys into porous SiC
4 and C-based materials [9-12] as well as SiC-C [13-16], SiC/C_f and SiC_f/SiC [17] are reported in
5 literature. Depending on the composition of the preform and in particular on the C-content, the
6 liquid metal infiltration evolves through Reaction Formed Silicon Carbide (RFSC) or Reaction
7 Bonded Silicon Carbide (RBSC) mechanisms and β -SiC is produced at the interface [5-7]. In
8 addition, reactive infiltration can be successful used to shape and join CMCs parts [18, 19].
9 Despite these advantages, the main drawback of these produced materials is the presence of
10 unreacted Si compromising the overall mechanical performance of the composite. Moreover, if C
11 and C-fibers are the reinforcements, their reaction with Si may result in the pore narrowing
12 phenomenon [20–22] and weakening of the composite [23, 24]. In addition, during solidification the
13 unreacted Si expands generating internal stresses and cracks [25].
14 The partial replacement of Si unreacted phase with intermetallic compounds (silicides) like MoSi₂
15 [26, 27], CoSi₂ [13, 28], ZrSi₂ [14], FeSi₂ [28, 29] was successfully obtained in the fabrication of
16 structural ceramic matrix composites for extremely high-temperature applications by infiltrating Si-
17 rich eutectic alloys into C-based and SiC-C preforms. However, in designing light-weight
18 composite materials, owing to their high density, the mentioned intermetallic phases can not be
19 considered.
20 As documented by [28], the selection of Si-Ti system represents a viable alternative worthy to be
21 taken into account in fabricating light-weight SiC-TiSi₂ composites. Indeed, a SiC-TiSi₂ composite
22 material should be resulting from spontaneous infiltration of a (SiC-particles) SiCp-C preform with
23 the liquid Si-Ti eutectic (Si-16.2at%Ti) alloy, at a processing temperature ranging from T = 1330°C
24 and T = 1450°C, under a vacuum or inert atmosphere. The composite obtained should exhibits a
25 density value around 3 g/cm³, increased thermo-mechanical properties, high inherent compatibility
26 and increased corrosion resistance. Additionally, among the refractory metal silicides, having TiSi₂
27 the lowest bulk resistivity [30], it has been found particularly attractive for low-temperature CMOS
28 applications [31].
29 As reported by [28], the resulting SiC_f/SiC composite obtained by infiltrating the liquid Si-Ti
30 eutectics into orthogonal three-dimensional SiC fiber preforms showed excellent mechanical
31 properties because the decomposition and degradation of the amorphous SiC fiber reinforcements
32 were prevented due the low-processing temperature imposed (T = 1330°C).
33 Despite the encouraging predictions, many aspects are not yet understood, mainly related to the
34 interfacial phenomena occurring during reactive infiltration process. Key contributions could be

1 coming from the know-how on the thermophysical properties of the melt phase, such as surface
2 properties (surface tension and surface segregation), density, viscosity, [32] and in parallel, on the
3 wetting characteristics and reactivity concerning reacting phases, as pointed out by [33].

4 To our best knowledge, the only one basic study on liquid Si enriched Si-Ti alloys are concerning
5 measurements of the surface tension [34] and fundamental wetting characteristics of such alloys on
6 SiC substrate [35].

7 For this reason, a systematic preliminary investigation on the wetting characteristics and reactivity
8 at Si-Ti eutectics/C and Si-Ti eutectics/SiC interfaces at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$ was performed by contact
9 heating (CH) sessile drop method. To overcome the affecting factor on the spreading behaviour
10 given by the presence SiO_2 -primary oxide, targeted experiments were performed by non-contact
11 heating combined with capillary purification sessile drop method [36], also named dispensed drop.

12 By analyzing wettability, spreading kinetics of the eutectic alloy on the selected substrates and all
13 the occurring interfacial reactions driving the growth of SiC reaction layer at the interface, the
14 present work aims to provide new findings helpful for defining the processes governing the kinetics
15 of reactive infiltration and the well known pore narrowing and pore closure phenomena.

16 **2. Wetting tests: experimental details**

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18 *2.1 Materials and sample preparation*

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20 Glassy Carbon (GC) provided by Alfa-Aesar was selected as C-substrate material and used with as
21 received surface conditions.

22 Hot-isostatic pressed SiC without free Si and sintering aids (as confirmed by X-Ray diffraction
23 analysis) provided (Goodfellows©) was selected as second substrate. The SiC substrates were
24 metallographically polished by 800-4000 SiC grinding and 1-0.5 μm diamond pastes.

25 The Si-16.2at%Ti alloy samples (from now Si-Ti eutectic alloy), were prepared by mixing nominal
26 weights of high purity Si and Ti (99.98%-Goodfellow®). To limit the evaporation phenomenon, the
27 alloy samples were produced by arc melting technique under an atmosphere of Ar (N60, $\text{O}_2 < 0.1$
28 ppm). Before the arc melting of Si-Ti alloys, the residual oxygen content inside the chamber was
29 reduced by melting a Zr drop. To ensure the homogeneity of the alloy composition, the melting of
30 every single Si-Ti sample (0,5 g) was repeated 3 times. No evidences of evaporation or material loss
31 were revealed by checking the final weight.

32 The as produced Si-Ti eutectic microstructure and composition was checked on the cross-sectioned
33 sample by SEM/EDS.

34 As it can be seen in Figure 1, the typical eutectic microstructure is detected with embedded some
35 TiSi_2 precipitates. The presence of TiSi_2 precipitates dispersed into the eutectic matrix is due to the
segregation of few layers of Si at the alloy surface during solidification.

1 Prior to the experiments, the alloy sample and substrate were rinsed in ethanol + US and dried with
2 compressed air.

12 **Figure 1.** BSE images at three magnifications of the cross-sectioned Si-Ti eutectic alloy sample as-produced.

13 *2.2 Methods*

14 For wetting tests at high temperature, the sessile drop method is the technique most widely used. As
15 shown in Figure 2a, a small piece of solid material, placed on a flat substrate is contact-heated (CH)
16 up to the selected testing temperature crossing different phase changing from solid to molten state.
17 Although this method is usually employed to obtain advancing contact angles, it may also lead to
18 receding contact angles, by increasing the ratio of the solid base diameter to solid height.

19 For binary metal systems or even more complex multicomponent alloys, a delaying melting is
20 typically observed due to several factors such as, oxidation at room temperature, as-produced
21 starting material with not homogenous composition, high reactivity in general or even highly
22 exothermic reactions occurring at the drop/substrate interface, not-isothermal heating along the
23 height of the sample, etc. In another variant, a metal or alloy is melted in an un-wetted, chemically
24 inert and stable closed ceramic capillary, then the molten phase is squeezed and dispensed onto the
25 fresh substrate through a hole using a piston, as shown in Figure 2b. One advantage of this second
26 technique is that within the squeezing, native oxide films are mechanically broken and removed,
27 thus a oxide-free molten surface is exposed to the surrounding experimental environment [36]. On
28 the other hand, such liquid free-oxide surface more readily might interact with the tip of the
29 capillary and to be more prone to further surface oxidation and evaporation phenomena.

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Figure 2. Sessile drop by a) Contact-heating and b) No-contact capillary purification methods.

2.3 Contact heating sessile drop experiments: device and procedure

At room temperature, the assembled Si-Ti eutectics/substrate (GC or SiC) couple was placed on a graphite sample holder and located at the central part of the heater. Once leveled the sample at horizontal plane, in order to remove any contaminant from the experimental environment, the device was degassed under a vacuum ($P_{\text{tot}} \leq 10^{-6}$ mbar) for two hours.

The alloy sample/substrate couple was heated under a Ar ($O_2 < 0.1$ ppm) atmosphere by a 800 kHz high frequency generator coupled to a graphite susceptor, as extensively described elsewhere [37]. The experiments were performed under an inert atmosphere in order to avoid evaporation phenomena typically occurring during measurements of liquid Si-based alloys [38] mainly over their melting temperature. The presence of graphite as heater element provides an atmosphere with reduced oxygen content ($PO_2 < 10^{-8}$ mbar).

During the wetting experiments, the temperature was in real time monitored by a pyrometer (Minolta-CYCLOPS52), previously calibrated by detecting the melting temperature of high purity metals (Sn, Al, Au, Cu, Si and Ni).

The wetting experiments were performed by achieving the isothermal conditions with a heating rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{sec}$. The selected temperature was kept constant for 15 minutes, then the sample was “quenched” (cooling rate $10^\circ/\text{sec}$) to “freeze” the new formed reaction products and interface microstructures.

The evolution of contact angles values over time was monitored in real-time and recorded (10 frames/sec) by a high resolution CCD-camera connected to a computer.

1 Every single frame was processed by an image analysis software ad hoc-developed
2 (ASTRAVIEW®) [40] allowing the automatic acquisition of contact angles and drop geometric
3 variables (R-base radius and H-drop height). By analyzing the experimental method used and all the
4 possible affecting factors, the accuracy of the contact angle value is estimated around $\pm 2^\circ$ [36].

5 *2.4 Non-contact heating and capillary purification sessile drop experiments: device and procedure*

6 The experimental complex located at FRI of Krakow, described in details in [41], was used to study
7 the wettability and spreading kinetics of Si-Ti eutectics/GC by squeezing the melted alloy on fresh
8 GC substrate at $T = 1450^\circ\text{C}$ under a static Ar atmosphere.

9 It is worthy to be pointed out that the presence of Ta as heating element, itself surrounded with Ta
10 and Mo isolation screens, acting as an oxygen getter, assures an oxygen partial pressure inside the
11 test chamber that is imposed by thermodynamics of the $(4/5) \text{Ta} + \text{O}_2 = (2/5) \text{Ta}_2\text{O}_5$ reaction [42].
12 Accordingly, at the working temperature $T = 1450^\circ\text{C}$, the oxygen partial pressure value of
13 $\text{PO}_2 < 10^{-14}$ mbar was obtained.

14 The alloy sample was stored into a Al_2O_3 polycrystalline capillary (diameter 9 mm), loaded inside
15 the chamber and kept under a vacuum overnight.

16 In order to remove residual gases, the chamber was heated up to $T = 800^\circ\text{C}$ ($10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) under a
17 vacuum. At this temperature the inert gas (static Ar, $P_{\text{tot}} = 850\text{-}900$ mbar) was introduced into the
18 chamber in order to suppress the evaporation of Si, then the chamber was heated up to testing
19 temperature.

20 At $T = 1450^\circ\text{C}$, the capillary was moved into the high temperature zone where the melted alloy was
21 squeezed through a hole (diameter 1 mm) by a piston and the formed drop was deposited onto the
22 substrate (Figure 2).

23 At the end of the isothermal time ($t = 15$ min) the chamber was cooled from 1450°C to room
24 temperature with a rate of $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

25 The drop/substrate profiles images were recorded for the whole duration of the experiment by a
26 high-speed digital camera (1-100 frames/s). Due to the high temperature emissivity, IRcut-off filters
27 were used.

28 Every single frame was processed by ASTRAVIEW® software and the contact angle values,
29 geometric parameters of the drop were measured allowing to obtain the evolution of wettability and
30 spreading behaviours over time.

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33 *2.5. Surface and microstructural characterization*

34 After wetting tests all the Si-Ti eutectics/GC and Si-Ti eutectics/SiC samples were embedded in
epoxy-resin, cross-sectioned and polished using standard metallographic procedure (800-4000

1 grinding SiC papers and 1 μm polishing diamond paste) and prepared for the microstructural
2 characterization. In order to analyze the microstructure and reaction products, both at the top and at
3 the cross-sectioned solidified drop, a Optical Microscope (OM-Keyence VHX-700F) and a
4 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM-Hitachi TM3000) equipped with an energy dispersive X-Ray
5 detectors (EDS) were used.

6 **3. Results**

7 *3.1 Surface roughness*

8 The surface roughness values of GC and SiC, measured on an area of $3 \times 3 \text{ mm}^2$ by an optical
9 confocal-interferometric profilometer (Sensofar S-neox), were resulting $R_a \approx 20 \text{ nm}$ and $R_a \approx 0.5$
10 μm , respectively.

11 *3.2 Wettability by contact-heating sessile drop method*

12 In Figure 3, the images sequence of Si-Ti eutectics spreading on both GC and SiC substrates at $T =$
13 1450°C under an Ar atmosphere, are shown. Although, as reported by [43], the isothermal
14 temperature is 120°C higher than the melting temperature of Si-16.2at%Ti eutectic composition (T_m
15 $= 1330^\circ\text{C}$), a delay in the complete melting was observed on both the substrates. In particular, as
16 soon as a liquid phase appeared in contact with SiC, the alloy started to wet SiC even if the upper
17 part of the drop was partially melted.
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Figure 3. Time sequence images recorded during the early-stage of spreading of Si-Ti eutectics on: a) SiC and b) GC at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$.

When the complete melting was observed at the Si-Ti eutectics/SiC interface ($t = 15\text{ s}$) a contact angle value of $\theta \approx 50^{\circ}$ was measured. At $t = 25\text{ s}$, the measured contact angle was $\theta \approx 43^{\circ}$ and this value was kept constant until the end of the experiments. Contrarily, at Si-Ti eutectics/GC interface, the complete melting of the alloy sample took $t = 3\text{ s}$ to form a spherical alloy drop on GC substrate displaying a contact angle value of $\theta \approx 105^{\circ}$ and 12 seconds to exhibit a wetting behavior ($\theta < 90^{\circ}$). The equilibrium at Si-Ti eutectics/GC interface was achieved in 45 seconds with a measured contact angle of $\theta \approx 44^{\circ}$.

Such relevant steps concerning the spreading of Si-Ti eutectics on GC and SiC substrates at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$

can be evinced by analyzing the kinetics of wettability both the couples as shown in Figure 4.

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Figure 4. Contact angle values as a function of time of Si-Ti eutectics/SiC (●) and Si-Ti eutectics/GC (○) at T = 1450°C measured by contact-heating sessile drop method.

In particular, as it can be seen in the inserted plot where the measured contact angles within the first 100 s are reported, the differences observed in the Si-Ti eutectics wettability on GC and SiC within the first seconds after the detected melting are evident.

As already introduced, the same equilibrium contact angle value of $\theta \approx 43\text{-}44^\circ$ was measured in Si-Ti/GC and Si-Ti/SiC systems at the end of isothermal times but with different spreading kinetics. Specifically, at the Si-Ti/SiC interface, the equilibrium was achieved 4 times faster than in Si-Ti/GC system.

Fig. 5 shows the triple lines of Si-Ti eutectics/GC and Si-Ti eutectics/SiC systems for a holding time of 15 minutes. At the triple line of both couples, a shadow surrounding the drop perimeter, is revealed. In particular, several SiC crystals are detected close the Si-Ti eutectic alloy drop onto GC. In addition, moving far from the triple line, unreacted regions of GC appear with over-layered circular and narrowing areas of SiC. On the contrary, the growth of SiC crystals is less pronounced at Si-Ti eutectics/SiC triple line confirming that the wettability at Si-Ti eutectics/GC interface is mainly driven by reactivity.

1 **Figure 5.** BSE analysis at the top of the solidified a) Si-Ti eutectic alloy/GC and b) Si-Ti eutectic alloy/SiC
2 couples after wetting tests performed at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$ by contact-heating sessile drop method.

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4 The Si-Ti eutectics/GC and Si-Ti eutectics/SiC interface microstructures developed at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$
5 for an holding time of 15 minutes are shown in Figure 6.

6 Figures 6a and 6b show the SEM images of the cross-sectioned solidified alloy droplets on the two
7 substrates.

8 As first evidence, a crack at the interfaces was detected and most probably generated during the fast
9 cooling of the samples.

10 A compact SiC layer was detected as unique reaction product at Si-Ti eutectics/GC triple line with
11 an average thickness of 5-7 μm , as shown in Figure 6 c. A different microstructure developed at the
12 alloy/GC interface far from the triple line. A double layering of reaction products, namely a
13 compact layer of SiC with a thickness of 3 μm and faceted SiC crystals with a size of 5-7 μm was
14 detected (see Figure 6 e).

15 Contrarily, as non-reactive system, absence of reaction layer was revealed between Si-Ti eutectics
16 and the SiC substrate, as shown in Figure 6 d. Nevertheless, a slight erosion of the SiC substrate at
17 the alloy/SiC interface was evidenced (see Figure 6 f).

18 In both cases, the solidified alloy drop exhibits a Si-TiSi₂ two phase microstructure. In particular,
19 rounded and needle shaped TiSi₂ crystals embedded in a Si-matrix.

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1 **Figure 6.** BSE images at different magnifications performed at the cross-sectioned a), c), e) Si-Ti eutectic
2 alloy/GC and b), d), f) Si-Ti eutectic alloy/SiC couples after wetting tests at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$ by contact heating
3 sessile drop method.

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5 3.3 Wettability by capillary-purified sessile drop method

6 The contact angle values as a function of time of Si-Ti eutectics in contact with GC measured at $T =$
7 1450°C under an Ar atmosphere by capillary-purified sessile drop method, are shown in Figure 7.

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10 **Figure 7.** Contact angle values as a function of time of Si-Ti eutectics/GC (■) measured at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$ by
11 capillary purified sessile drop method.

12 The perturbation on the contact angle behaviour occurred just after the drop deposition onto the GC
13 substrate was caused by the mechanical stress resulting by the rising up of the capillary, even
14 evinced by the plot inserted into the Figure 7 and by the time sequence images shown in Figure 8.

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16 **Figure 8.** Time sequence images recorded during the squeezing, deposition and spreading of liquid Si-Ti
17 eutectics drop on GC at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$.

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1 A contact angle value of $\theta \approx 97^\circ$ was measured at the end of perturbation ($t > 1.8$ s). Within the
2 following 0.5 s, the Si-Ti eutectics/GC started to display a wetting behavior ($\theta < 90^\circ$). The
3 equilibrium at Si-Ti eutectics/GC interface was reached in 9 seconds where a steady state contact
4 angle value of $\theta \approx 41^\circ$ was measured at the triple line.

5 On the GC substrate, a shadow beyond the alloy perimeter is present and resulting from narrowing
6 circular thin layers of SiC, as shown in Figure 9.

18 **Figure 9.** BSE analysis at the top of the solidified Si-Ti eutectic alloy/GC couple after wetting test
19 performed at $T = 1450^\circ\text{C}$ by capillary purified sessile drop method.

21 Figures 10a and 10b show the SEM images of the cross sectioned solidified alloy drop onto GC
22 substrate. The solidified alloy drop microstructure developed both rounded and needle shaped TiSi_2
23 crystals embedded in a Si matrix (Figure 10 a). As previously, a fractured interface was observed
24 caused by the fast cooling of the sample down to room temperature.

25 A compact SiC layer was detected as unique reaction product (as confirmed by EDS analyses) at Si-
26 Ti eutectics/GC triple line with an average thickness of 5-7 μm (Figure 10 b) with few faceted SiC-
27 crystals. A different microstructure developed far from the triple line. Specifically, a compact layer
28 of SiC with a thickness of 3 μm and a packed overlayer of faceted SiC crystals epitaxially growth
29 with a size of 7-10 μm (Figure 10 c).

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2 **Figure 10.** BSE/EDS analyses at different magnifications performed at the cross-sectioned Si-Ti eutectic
 3 alloy/GC couple after wetting tests at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$ by capillary purified sessile drop method.

4 **4. Discussion**

5 As evidenced by SEM/EDS analyses performed on the as-produced alloy sample, alternating pure Si
 6 and TiSi_2 were detected as segregating phases at the surface. The melting temperatures of pure Si
 7 and Ti-disilicide are $T = 1414^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T = 1480^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively, thus higher than the melting
 8 temperature of Si-16.2at%Ti alloy [43]. In addition, both the constituents exhibit high tendency to
 9 interact with oxygen and to form stable oxides at the surface even at room temperature [42]. For
 10 these mentioned reasons, even if the imposed isothermal temperature was 120°C higher than the
 11 melting temperature of Si-16.2at%Ti eutectic composition ($T_m = 1330^{\circ}\text{C}$), a delay in the complete
 12 melting of Si-Ti eutectics alloy sample was observed in contact to both the substrates within the
 13 contact heating sessile drop experiments. According to the SEM/EDS analyses, Si content at the
 14 surface is more pronounced than Ti so it can be assumed that SiO_2 is predominant as native oxide
 15 phase covering the alloy sample.

16 The layer of native oxide is decomposed by its reaction with the underlying liquid Si, forming the
 17 volatile Si monoxide [42, 44]:

2 In addition, the further delay of 3 second displayed by the alloy drop in spreading onto the SiC
 3 substrate can be due to the higher roughness of the SiC surface (1 μm) respect to the GC substrate
 4 (20 nm) and by the presence of SiO_2 at the SiC surface which undergoes to decomposition by the
 5 following above mentioned reaction (1).

6 As it is well known, SiC is well-wettable substrate by liquid Si and Si-based alloys [44, 45].
 7 Moreover, Si and Si-based alloys/SiC are non-reactive systems. Contrarily, Si and Si-based alloys
 8 do not wet but strongly react with C by the exothermic reaction [44]:

10 Consequently, the local increase of temperature could be a concomitant factor promoting the
 11 decomposition of the SiO_2 layer (by reaction 1) covering the alloy drop in contact with GC substrate.

12 Figure 11 shows the spreading kinetics observed within the first 100 seconds of the contact-heating
 13 sessile drop experiments performed on Si-Ti eutectics/GC and Si-Ti eutectics/SiC systems.

14 **Figure 11.** Evolution of R-drop base radius over time of Si-Ti eutectics/SiC (●) and Si-Ti eutectics/GC (○)
 15 observed within contact-heating sessile drop experiments performed at $T = 1450^\circ\text{C}$.

16 As already introduced and in agreement with the literature [44], the equilibrium at the interface is
 17 faster achieved on SiC than GC substrate. It is given by the different spreading behaviour driven by
 18 wetting for non-reactive system and by chemical reaction-limited spreading for reactive-system
 19 [46], on SiC and GC, respectively. In particular, the spreading rate exhibited on SiC was around
 20 $U_{\text{spread}} \approx 92 \mu\text{m/s}$.

21 Analyzing the spreading behaviour on GC, three different stages can be identified with three
 22 different spreading rates. Within the first 23 seconds a linear spreading behaviour was observed
 23 ($U_{\text{spread}} \approx 52 \mu\text{m/s}$). In general, linear spreading behaviours are associated to reactive wetting [44,
 24

1 46]. At $t > 23$ s a decrease of 10 times in the slope of the spreading behavior over time was
 2 observed. Within this stage, the spreading behavior as a function of time is still well described by
 3 linear law, then might be still related to reactive mechanism at the interface but limited by the
 4 appearance of a competitive phenomenon such as the growth of a rougher reaction layer at the
 5 interface. The appearance of SiC layer and crystals at the interface, mainly at the triple line, and
 6 their gradual packaging, significantly reduce the wettability (by increased roughness) and decrease
 7 the diffusion path of Si-alloy through such crystals towards C substrate [47]. Consequently, C-
 8 dissolution is suppressed and the reaction kinetics slows down until its depletion which probably
 9 occurs at $t = 45$ seconds where no any evident advancing in the contact angle value was observed.
 10 Despite the affinity of both the alloy constituents for carbon [42, 43] to produce stable TiC and SiC
 11 ($\Delta G^{\circ}_{f\text{TiC}} = -276$ Kcal/mol and $\Delta G^{\circ}_{f\text{SiC}} = -147$ Kcal/mol), at this temperature and for a Ti-content
 12 of 16.2at% into the alloy, the reaction of liquid Si to produce SiC at the interface, is
 13 thermodynamically more favored respect to the production of TiC or ternary carbides [48] as
 14 confirmed by the SEM/EDS analyses performed at the interfaces (Figures 6 and 10).
 15 Figure 12 shows the first 100 seconds of the Si-Ti eutectics/GC wetting kinetics obtained by contact
 16 heating and capillary-purified sessile drop methods. Comparing the two contact angle behaviors as a
 17 function of time, the influence of the starting conditions (composition, oxide free surface) on the
 18 wetting kinetics are evident. In the capillary-purified sessile drop, the early stage of spreading is not
 19 coexistent with the alloy melting. In addition, the absence of any oxide phase segregated at the
 20 surface of the substrate, at the surface of the alloy drop and at the triple line, does not affect the
 21 reaction kinetics between liquid Si and C, as well as the wetting kinetics at Si-Ti eutectics/GC
 22 interface.

23
 24 **Figure 12.** Contact angles values of Si-Ti eutectics/GC measured at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$ by contact heating (○) and
 25 capillary-purified (■) sessile drop methods.

1
2 Moreover, in spite the affinity of liquid Si and Ti for oxygen to form at the surface stable oxides, at
3 $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$ further oxidation or oxygen transport at the alloys surface can be neglected by the
4 presence of counter flows of volatile mono-oxides (SiO , TiO and TiO_2), as demonstrated by [49,
5 50]. In addition, owing to the high evaporation tendency of liquid Si [42], condensed Si and Si-
6 oxide fogs might be present in the gas phase surrounding the drop, acting as a barrier and
7 suppressing the O_2 -flow coming from the atmosphere to the alloy surface [51]. Such phenomenon
8 can explain the growth of circular area of SiC detected far from the triple line.

9 Despite the pronounced evaporation observed at the Si-Ti eutectics/GC triple line at $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$,
10 the consequent formation of a thin reaction layer beyond the triple line does not enable the further
11 advancement of contact angle as observed for Si-Co eutectic alloy/GC at the same temperature [33].
12 It can be justified by the different molten phase. Si-Ti eutectics and TiSi_2 silicide phase exhibit a
13 lower density than Si-Co eutectics and CoSi_2 [52]. In addition, the surface tension of Si-Ti is little
14 bit higher than Si-Co [32,34]. The lower density combined with a higher surface tension of the
15 molten phase could allow a more stability of the molten alloy Si-Ti eutectics drop on the GC
16 substrate respect to Si-Co eutectics one.

17 The contact angle value ($\theta \approx 41^{\circ}$) measured at the start of steady state condition at Si-Ti
18 eutectics/GC interface obtained by capillary purified sessile drop is comparable with the value
19 measured within the contact heating experiments ($\theta \approx 44^{\circ}$) and in agreement with the literature [25].
20 The difference can be justified by the different methods applied and consequently by the different
21 accuracy.

22 Moreover, the contact angle values measured between liquid Si-Ti eutectics and GC substrates are
23 in good agreement with the contact angle displayed at the Si-Ti eutectics/SiC ($\theta \approx 42^{\circ}$) confirming
24 that the contact angle values observed at the equilibrium are in real the contact angles between
25 liquid Si-Ti eutectic alloy and SiC as stated by [25].

26 As already introduced, few basic studies performed on liquid Si enriched Si-Ti alloys in terms of
27 surface tension [34] and fundamental wetting characteristics on SiC substrate [35] are available in
28 literature. In particular, a surface tension value of $\gamma = 1112 \text{ mN/m}$ measured on Si-12.4at%Ti at $T =$
29 1450°C by sessile drop method under He is reported by [34]. At the same temperature, the
30 calculated surface tension by applying ideal solution model is significantly lower $\gamma = 734 \text{ mN/m}$
31 than the measured value [52]. The difference might be explained by the higher Si-content into the
32 alloy under study in this work. In addition, the ideal solution approach may lead to under estimate
33 the real phenomenon. Moreover, in spite of the no-wettable behaviour between liquid Si and BN at
34 $T = 1450^{\circ}\text{C}$, BN dissolution in molten Si (the dissolution rate depends on temperature) was

1 documented by [53, 54]. The presence of B dissolved into the liquid Si can increase the surface
2 tension of the alloy drop. Taking into account such considerations, the contact angle value measured
3 on SiC ($\theta \approx 42^\circ$) is comparable with the value reported on Si-7at%Ti [35].
4

5 **5. Conclusions**

6 Wettability and reactivity studies of liquid Si-16.2at%Ti eutectic composition in contact with GC
7 and SiC were performed at $T = 1450^\circ\text{C}$ under an atmosphere with reduced oxygen content by
8 contact heating sessile drop method.

9 Aiming to increase the reliability of the results, under the same operating conditions, targeted
10 experiments were performed even by no contact heating capillary purified sessile drop method.

11 As evinced by comparing the results obtained by the two different experimental methods, the early
12 stage of wettability, in terms of spreading kinetics, is strongly dependent on the starting conditions.
13 In particular, within the melting stage, combined factors such as the presence of Si, TiSi_2 and SiO_2
14 as native oxide, segregated at the surface of the starting alloy material affected evidently the early-
15 stage of the alloy spreading on the GC and SiC substrates.

16 Such mentioned factors and the different sessile drop methods applied seem not affecting the final
17 contact angle values which are in agreement with the available literature.

18 Clear evidences were obtained and confirmation that the wettability and in particular the spreading
19 kinetics on GC are controlled by the growing and thickening of SiC as unique reaction product at
20 the interface and at the triple line.

21 The results obtained can be helpful to identify the key parameters affecting the manufacturing of
22 SiC/ TiSi_2 composite materials. Nevertheless, the reactivity of liquid Si-Ti alloys on C should be
23 extended by estimating the influence of Si-content and isothermal time on the SiC growth which is
24 mainly responsible for the pore closure/narrowing phenomena affecting the kinetics of infiltration.

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26
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